

ISic3114

I.Sicily inscription 3114

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

column

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.04.18

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

A funerary stele in the form of a fluted column supporting a rectangular block bearing the inscribed field (the block is 26cm high by 57 cm wide)

Dimensions

Height 75 cm

Width 37 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Four lines of Greek text, engraved in stucco and painted in red, across the full width of the rectangular block, with a vacant below.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐσθλὸν ἐν ἀγκοίνησιν ἔχ[ωξένο]ν, ὦ παροδίτα
2. φῶτα Ποσειδερμον, Μασσαλ[ίης] ναέτην
3. Πυθαγόρεω φίλον υἷα τὸν ἐνθάδ[εμ]οῖρα κραταιή
4. πλάγξασα ἐκ πάτρης τήλε φίλ[ης] ὄλεσεν

Apparatus

Text of Manni Piraino

Translation (it)

Tengo fra le braccia, o passeggero, un eccellente uomo straniero, Poseidermos, abitante di Marsiglia e figlio caro di Pitagora, che la Moira violenta ha ucciso dopo averlo trascinato lungi dalla cara patria

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284790

EDCS 64900329

PHI 331222

Bibliography

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